

COVID-19 VACCINATION SAFETY AMONG GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING STUDENTS OF AMBROSE ALLI UNIVERSITY, EKPOMA, EDO STATE.

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Abstract

The study investigated issues of COVID-19 vaccination safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, as well as the perceived benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among the students. The study adopted the descriptive method of research design. The population consisted of all 131 Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University. Since the sample size was small, the entire population was used as the sample. Hence, no sampling technique was employed to draw a sample from the students. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. Based on findings, the researcher concluded by suggesting that students of Ambrose Alli University are aware of COVID-19, the risk factors associated with contracting it, and the preventive measures required to avoid infection.

Keywords: Covid-19, Counselling Students, Vaccines, Diseases

Introduction

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), a rapidly spreading respiratory viral illness with significant morbidity and fatality rates, has dominated public health debates throughout the world. Since 2019, the disease has swiftly expanded, assisted mostly by international air travel, to encompass every area of the world, forcing the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare a global COVID-19 pandemic on 30th January, 2020. It continues to pose a significant danger to global public health (Hyland et al., 2021). As observed by Oaikhena and Aligbe, (2023), "it is the duty of society to prevent the strong, greedy, and

unscrupulous individuals from exploiting the weak and over-enriching themselves at their expense”.

Coronavirus, a respiratory tract illness considered to have been transmitted initially from animals to people at Wuhan, China—other schools of thought say a laboratory leak, which has symptoms that include fever with high or low grade, and cough. This is generally from persistent body weakness, headache, and vomiting in some cases (Dolgin, 2021). Contact with cough droplets, which might be on the hands of cough sufferers or resting on surfaces such as door handles, in some circumstances, touching the face, nose, and mouth with the same hands, is known to transmit it. Over 273 million cases and 5.3 million fatalities from COVID-19 and associated disorders had been documented globally as of 21st December (WHO, 2021). With a rising number of cases and deaths worldwide, there was a global panic, and the WHO quickly proposed preventive means to curb the disease’s spread. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Aligbe (2023) posit that “to overcome limitations, government and individuals have to render their co-operation to group efforts, so that together they could achieve more and meet target group demands”.

In view of these, regular handwashing/hand sanitizing, maintaining social distance of at least 6 meters apart, regular disinfecting of surfaces, especially in public areas, wearing of face masks, especially in public, isolation of suspected people, widespread availability of testing facilities, and counselling and testing when feeling symptoms was advised. The COVID-19 pandemic remains a major problem among the world to date. There are reports of increasing numbers of unexplained deaths in various communities in the country (Elimian et al., 2024), but the extent to which these are related to the COVID-19 pandemic has not been systematically investigated. It is not clear how various groups in the country perceive individual and group risks for the virus, and how they have responded to various interventions designed to mitigate the infection.

The release of safe and effective COVID-19 vaccinations by multiple pharmaceutical firms in 2020 marked a significant milestone. Vaccination was thus highlighted as a vital, game-changing instrument in the battle against COVID-19, with a focus on equitable global access to vaccination (WHO, 2020). This comment emphasized

that despite the availability of vaccinations, there must be equal access to them and a desire to take them, which must be equitably shared and accepted around the world, because vaccines will not halt the pandemic, but immunization would (WHO, 2020).

Vaccines have previously been used with great effectiveness to help prevent the spread or eliminate the severity of illness all around the world. It is a normal practice in many countries to administer immunizations to newborns at birth in order to avoid endemic illnesses. This method has been shown to reduce the spread, severity, and incidence of certain endemic diseases (Briisow, 2021). However, successes in the field of children's immunization did not occur without early hurdles of hesitation, which were exacerbated by misconceptions, misinformation, and disinformation. Currently, there is a sizeable anti-vaccine group whose beliefs are based on the notion that vaccinations are hazardous—issues bolstered by misconceptions and conspiracy theories surrounding vaccination (Lodish, 2000).

Statement of the Problem

The COVID-19 vaccine has raised several issues among students and people in the public domain. Issues of vaccine safety in relation to the reproductive and mental health of people. Some questioned whether the producers of the vaccine may have hurriedly developed the vaccines to make more money and in doing so produced something hazardous that could cause more harm than good to human health. According to Oaikhena (2021) he rightly observed that, “the lack of formal economic opportunities, combined with the legacy of entrenched political conflicts and instability, as well as the rise of Covid-19 pandemic, high rates of malnutrition, illness, and poor education, poses many challenges on the African continent”.

Vaccine was also considered as religion based which heightened the fears of some people in the society. Church leaders such as Pastor Chris Oyakhilome openly stated that "the COVID-19 and the vaccine is a devil's scam at the church to suppress the faith of believers" (Ilesanme & Afolabi, 2020). It is against these backdrop that this study examined salient issues that mitigated COVID-19 vaccination safety amongst Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Purpose of the Study

The main concern of this study is to examine the issues of COVID-19 vaccination; to examine the need for the COVID-19 vaccine; to examine the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety; and to examine the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study: i) What are the issues on the need for the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State? ii) What are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State? iii) What are the issues concerning the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?

Design of the Study

This study adopted the descriptive study design. Sekaran (2013) defined descriptive survey research as one in which information is collected without changing the environment or manipulating the variables of the study. He noted that it is a research design in which the researcher interacts with the participants through interviews or questionnaires to collect the necessary information. This design was employed in the study because the variables are not manipulated under controlled environmental or laboratory conditions. However, data collected from Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University would be presented in their natural setting to draw inferences.

Population

The population of the study consists of all 131 Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. These comprised of 24 students in 100

level, 19 students in 200 level, 56 in 300 level, and 32 in 400 level, in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Sampling

A sample of 131 Guidance and Counselling students was drawn. Since the sample size is relatively small and from a finite population, the entire population was used as the sample. Hence, no sampling technique was employed to draw the sample.

Instrument

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was titled: *Issues of COVID-19 Survey Questionnaire (ICSQ)*. The instrument was divided into Sections A and B.

Section A contains information on the personal data of students, that is, sex, and age bracket of the students. While section B contains item statements bordering on the subject focus of the study, that is, issues of COVID-19 vaccination (items 11–15). Each item was rated on a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree – 4; Agree – 3; Disagree – 2; Strongly Disagree – 1.

Validity and reliability of study

The face and content validity of the instrument was carried out by the researcher and two other experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. Copies of the questionnaire were presented to them for corrections, and the amendments made were incorporated into the final draft to ensure the contents of the instrument were clear and relevant.

The test-retest reliability method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. This procedure was carried out by administering copies of the instrument to 30 students outside the study sample, within the study area. After a few weeks, the same instrument was re-administered to the same respondents. Their responses in the first and second tests were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation technique. The

result of the coefficient is expected to produce an r -value of 0.70 or higher, to show that the instrument is reliable.

Data Analysis

Research Questions 1, 2, and 3 were analyzed using the mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (S.D.). A mean score of 2.50 was used as the criterion mean for determining students' perception of the issues. This was obtained by adding the four Likert scale points (Strongly Agree – 4, Agree – 3, Disagree – 2, and Strongly Disagree – 1) and dividing the sum (10) by the total number of scale options (4), giving 2.50. The research questions were analyzed with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), IBM Version 20.

S/N	Item statements	X	S.D	Remarks
1.	COVID-19 is a scam and not real	2.71	1.040	Agreed
2.	COVID-19 is as infectious as many claim	2.69	.968	Agreed
3.	COVID-19 is a strategy of the government to loot public funds	2.36	1.041	Disagreed
4.	COVID-19 is dead and does not exist anymore	2.25	1.011	Disagreed
5.	I do not believe I can be affected with COVID-19	2.41	1.028	Disagreed

Results

Research question 1: What are the issues on the need for COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State?

Table 1: *Mean and standard score on the issues on the Need for COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State.*

Overall mean score= 2.42

Significant mean $\bar{x} > 2.50$

Results in *Table 1* showed that students have the awareness on items 1 and 2 at a mean score range of 2.69 and to 2.71 respectively. The overall mean score of 2.63 is lesser than the criterion mean of 2.50 (i.e. $X = 2.42 < 2.50$). Hence the result showed that COVID-19 is a scam and not real and COVID-19 is as infectious as many claims are the issues on the need for COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Research question 2: what are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State

Table 2: *mean and standard score on issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State*

S/N	Issues of COVID-19 safety	X	S.D	Remarks
1.	I think taking COVID-19 vaccine is taking the harmful virus itself	2.64*	1.068	Agreed
2.	I think the vaccine will give me the sign of the antichrist that us against my religion	2.59*	1.089	Agreed
3	I think the vaccine has a microchip designed to control me after sometime	2.62*	1.149	Agreed
4	Taking the vaccine will bring about a side effect sooner or later	2.58	1.170	Agreed
5	The reports of other that have taken it is not good enough to encourage acceptance	2.28	.988	Disagreed
	Overall mean score= 2.64			

Significant mean ($x \geq 2.50$)

Results in Table 2 showed that students agreed with Item 1, 2, 3, and 4 at a mean score ranging from 2.58 to 2.6, while they disagreed on Item 5 at a mean score of 2.8, respectively. The overall mean score of 2.64 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 (i.e.

$X = 2.64 > 2.50$). Hence, the result showed that respondents think taking the COVID-19 vaccine is equivalent to taking the harmful virus itself; that the vaccine has a microchip designed to control them after some time; and that taking the vaccine will bring about a side effect sooner or later. These are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Research Question 3: What are the issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation score on the Benefits of COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State.

S/N	ITEMS	X	S.D	REMARKS
1.	Us live without fear of staying in social gathering with people	2.72	1.014	Agreed
2	Reduce the spread of the virus from person to person	2.75	1.062	Agreed
3.	Reduce the health damage caused by the virus	2.57	1.062	Agreed
4.	Reduce the fear if contracting the virus by handshake	2.62	.976	Agreed
5.	Reduce the fear of contracting the virus by touching items in publicity used facilities	2.71	.909	Agreed
	Overall mean score= 2.53			

Significant $y(x > 2.50)$

Discussions

Findings from the study were discussed under the following sub-headings:

- The issues on the need for the COVID-19 vaccine
- The issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety
- The issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine

The Issues on the Need for the COVID-19 Vaccine:

The result showed that the belief that COVID-19 is a scam and not real, and that it is not as infectious as many claim, are the issues surrounding the need for the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The result is in line with that of Claide et al. (2021), who found that prior vaccination views and anxiety about the pace of testing and licensing of vaccines were the most predictive variables (p.007). Multivariate analysis confirmed these findings, while additionally revealing that perceived personal risk was significant ($P = 0.033$). The result also corroborates the findings of Shahid et al. (2021), who revealed that 52% and 48% of hospital employees, respectively, were willing and refused the corona vaccine. This study is notable for its use of mixed methodologies, including qualitative approaches to analyze socio-demographic effects and evaluate issues.

The result agreed with that of Amirhossein et al. (2021), who found relationships between female gender, higher age, and higher education and knowledge, attitude, and practice of Iranians during the COVID-19 pandemic, and vaccine approval. The result supported that of Dzieciolowka et al. (2021), who stated that the novelty of the vaccination, the desire for others to have it first, and limited time for decision-making were all reasons for rejection. The result is in consonance with that of Efani et al. (2020), who revealed a substantial relationship between female gender, older age, and greater education with knowledge, attitude, and practice.

The Issues of COVID-19 Vaccine Safety:

The result showed that respondents think taking the COVID-19 vaccine is equivalent to taking the harmful virus itself; that the vaccine will give them the sign of the Antichrist, which is against their religion; that the vaccine has a microchip designed to control them after some time; and that taking the vaccine will bring about side effects sooner or later. These are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2023) observed that “it is attributable to the characteristics of individuals and populations to deal with the primordial objective of surviving”.

The Issues on the Benefits of the COVID-19 Vaccine:

The result showed that living without fear of being in social gatherings with people, reducing the spread of the virus from person to person, reducing the health damage caused by the virus, reducing the fear of contracting the virus through handshakes, and reducing the fear of contracting the virus by touching items in publicly used facilities are among the issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Results in Table 3 showed that students agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 at a mean score ranging from 2.57 to 2.75, respectively. The overall mean score of 2.53 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 (i.e. $\bar{x} = 2.53 > 2.50$). Hence, the result showed that living without fear of being in social gatherings with people, reducing the spread of the virus from person to person, reducing the health damage caused by the virus, and reducing the fear of contracting the virus through touching items in publicly used facilities are the issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that students in secondary schools are aware of COVID-19 in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State. Students are also aware that risk factors for contracting COVID-19 include rubbing hands on frequently touched

surfaces, staying in close contact with infected persons, shaking hands with infected persons, ignoring the use of nose masks, and maintaining social closeness with people in crowded places. While practicing hand washing with clean water and soap, avoiding shaking hands with people, covering one's mouth while coughing, self-isolation, and maintaining social distancing are recognized as control strategies for COVID-19 among secondary school students in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State.

Recommendations

Based on findings from the study, the following were recommended:

1. More emphasis should be placed on updating knowledge regarding the diagnosis and treatment components of the COVID-19 disease. Interactive educational webinars can be conducted, focusing primarily on the pandemic and the disaster management of such infectious diseases.
2. It is imperative to commence early education and training of students to have in-depth knowledge to allay their fears and concerns. This will help change the narrative and their perception, enabling them to become good ambassadors and beacons of advocacy for the vaccine, in order to prevent mortality from the pandemic.

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